

A new method for community detection in academic heterogeneous networks

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Abstract

Identifying the community structure of a network through community detection can reveal the internal structural characteristics and attributes of the network. In the field of library and information, most research works are based on the community detection of single-author cooperative network or article citing network. The community detection in a heterogeneous network can dig out hidden communities and reveal the scientific structure from different perspectives. Therefore, author and article nodes are selected in the present research to construct an academic heterogeneous network including author-paper working relationship, paper citation relationship, author cooperation relationship, and author citation relationship. MESME-SLPA community detection method for the academic heterogeneous network is proposed, and DBLP dataset was selected to verify the effectiveness of the algorithm. At the same time, the frontier field of gene-editing technology was selected for empirical analysis, and verifies the advancement and effectiveness of community detection based on a heterogeneous network.

Keywords: Heterogeneous network, Community, Citation, Scientific structure, Gene-editing technology

Introduction

In real life, many individuals are not independent of each other, but are inextricably linked, and many interrelated individuals constitute a variety of complex systems. Networks are an important form to describe complex systems, such as social networks, neural networks, computer service networks, etc. The above-mentioned networks can be abstracted into a heterogeneous network composed of nodes of the same or different types and the relationships between these nodes. Heterogeneous networks refer to the networks satisfy the object type $|A| > 1$ and the relationship type $|R| > 1$. Compared with a single homogeneous network, a heterogeneous network can effectively fuse more information and contain richer semantics in objects and links, and plays a key role in mining network information (Sun & Han, 2012). Heterogeneous networks research is one of the most active hot research fields in recent years (Newman, 2018), which has been successfully applied in many fields (Wasserman & Galaskiewicz, 1994; Bader & Hogue, 2003; Sporns, 2010). In the field of library and information, it is mainly used to analyze the network structure or evolution characteristics based on cooperative relationship and citation relationship, which allows a better understanding of cooperation and citation mechanisms in a discipline field. Heterogeneous networks research has important significance

for revealing the direction of field research, academic community and the development context of scientific structure.

With the development of scientific research, the trend of interdisciplinary has become more and more obvious, and the disciplinary boundaries have gradually disappeared. In scientific research, it has become more and more difficult to clearly reveal the scientific structure. Through the exploration of network properties, researchers find that the whole network is usually composed of several "communities", which are also called clusters or modules or vertices with common properties or the same role in the network (Fortunato, 2009). Community detection in the network can not only reveal the similarity between nodes. It can also reveal the internal working principles of the community, which helps to understand the network structural features and the latent semantic information.

Therefore, based on the above research background, this study aims to use a new community detection method to divide academic heterogeneous networks, and verify its effectiveness and feasibility in the field of "gene editing technology".

The paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we provide an overview of community detection methods for heterogeneous networks and construction of academic heterogeneous networks. In Section 3, we introduce the proposed method MESME-SLPA, and uses DBLP dataset to verify its effectiveness. In section 4, we select "gene editing technology" field, construct author-paper heterogeneous network to carry out community detection. Section 5 discusses and analyzes the results of community detection. Finally, Section 6 ends the paper with a discussion.

Related works

Community detection methods for heterogeneous networks

At present, the research of community detection methods in homogeneous network is a mature stage. However, scholars have not yet reached a consensus on the configuration principle of multi-type nodes in the same network and the weight scheme of different relationship edges in heterogeneous networks, so it is still insufficient to directly apply traditional community detection method in heterogeneous networks. Most researchers on community detection methods in heterogeneous networks are mainly focused on the following two methods: one is to extend existing algorithms to directly deal with heterogeneous networks; the other is to reduce the dimension of heterogeneous networks to homogeneous networks and then carry out community detection (Tang & Liu, 2010; Berlingerio et al., 2011; Suthers et al., 2013). Based on the above two partitioning ideas, there are mainly five types of community detection methods in multi-node and multi-relationship heterogeneous networks.

Probabilistic model-based methods

Methods based on probabilistic model include methods based on ranking and probabilistic statistical models. RankClus (Sun et al., 2009) is the earliest proposed ranking clustering algorithm based on heterogeneous network, but it is only suitable for two types of nodes. Subsequently, the algorithms NetClus (Sun & Han, 2009), RankClass (Ji et al., 2011), EnetClus (Gupta et al., 2011), and OcdRank (Qiu et al., 2015) have been proposed successively to make it suitable for heterogeneous networks of any network mode and achieve community detection in dynamic heterogeneous networks.

Since the ranking-based methods need to set the number of communities in advance and is unstable, scholars propose to use Bayesian model, posterior probability methods to calculate the probability of nodes belonging to communities, so as to achieve the purpose of community detection. Heterogeneous networks spectral clustering algorithm (Sengupta & Chen, 2015) and ComClus algorithm (Wang et al., 2013) for random block model were proposed, which used probability model to represent the generation probability of objects, but did not solve the overlapping community problem.

Meta-paths based methods

Multiple types of nodes are connected by multiple links, and links connecting different nodes contain different semantics. Such links form meta-paths (Sun & Han, 2012), which can capture rich semantic information in heterogeneous networks (Sun & Han, 2011; Shi et al., 2017; Shi & Yu, 2017). PathSim (Sun & Han, 2011) is the earliest meta-path-based algorithm proposed for homogeneous networks. Shi et al. (2012) proposed a similarity algorithm -- HeteSim, which can measure the same or different types of nodes based on meta-path, but it is not suitable for large-scale networks. Subsequently, Meng et al. (2014) proposed AvgSim, a similarity algorithm based on the double random walk of a given meta-path and a reverse meta-path, which applied to large-scale networks. Li et al. (2018) eliminated the similarity bias based on PathSim's standardization, and designed a flexible fusion mechanism to dynamically optimize the results, so as to make the community detection results better. Meanwhile, PathSelClus (Sun et al., 2013) and Hrank (Shi & Yu, 2017) methods were proposed to evaluate the importance of nodes and meta-paths, in order to assign different weights to different meta-paths in heterogeneous networks.

Seed nodes-based methods

The seed-centric method has become an emerging trend of community detection algorithms (Hmimida & Kanawati, 2015). The basic idea of the method based on seed nodes is to identify some specific nodes in the network as seed nodes, and then build communities around these nodes (Kanawati, 2011; Papadopoulos et al., 2010; Shah & Zaman, 2010). Yakoubi et al. (2014) first proposed the seed node-driven community detection algorithm Licod, but this method is only applicable to homogeneous networks. Hmimida et al. (2015) extended Licod algorithm to heterogeneous network, called Mux-Licod, which considered different types of relationships between nodes in different layers of heterogeneous network. Experimental studies have shown that this method has good practicability.

Extended modularity methods

Modularity was first used to evaluate the results of community detection. Afterward, community detection algorithms based on modularity emerged (Newman & Girvan, 2004; Tang et al., 2009; Nicosia et al., 2009), which extends the modularity algorithm applicable to homogeneous networks to heterogeneous networks. The modularity optimization algorithm FN (Newman & Girvan, 2004) was first proposed by Newman et al., but it is only applicable to single-node networks. Guimera et al. (2007) and Murata & Ikeya (2010) respectively proposed modularity algorithms for bipartite networks and K-kernel networks, but none of them were universal. Liu et al. (2014) proposed the composite modularity method, which decomposed the heterogeneous networks into multiple subnetworks, integrated the modularity of each subnetwork and optimized the composite modularity. This method does not need prior knowledge and is suitable for large-scale networks.

Homogenous methods of heterogenous networks methods

Since the community detection methods of homogeneous network are relatively established, heterogeneous networks can be reduced into homogeneous networks, and then studied by homogeneous network community detection methods. Most of these methods include a dimensionality reduction process. Dimensionality reduction methods mainly include Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) (Lee & Seung, 1999), Subject Model, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Jolliffe, 2002), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) (Scholkopf & Mullert, 1999), etc.

Tafavogh (2014) proposed a heterogeneous network community detection method based on matrix factorization and semantic path, and experiments showed its effectiveness. Zhang et al. (2016) proposed a Non-Negative Matrix Three-Factorization (NMTF) method HMFClus, which integrates the information between objects of the same type into HMFClus by using similarity regularization and can cluster all types of objects in heterogeneous networks simultaneously. Liu et al. (2020) proposed a Penalized Alternative Factorization (PAF) algorithm for multi-layer attribute networks from the perspective of matrix factorization to solve the corresponding optimization problems, PAF method has strong applicability to network morphology (Liu et al., 2020). The topic model is introduced to mine the hidden topic information in the text to improve the effect of community detection. Mei et al. (2008) makes full use of the advantages of statistical topic model and discrete regularization to improve topic model through regularization and realize community detection. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) are both linear dimension reduction methods. The difference between them is that the former ensures that dimensionality reduced data retains more original information, while the latter makes it easier to be distinguished. The existing studies only apply these two methods to single-node networks (Lin et al., 2014; Li et al., 2016; Yuan et al., 2016) or binary networks (Liu & Chen, 2013).

Deep learning methods

The deep learning methods use a new community-oriented network representation to identify community structures, which has the advantages of low computational complexity and high parallelization ability (Jin et al., 2021). Existing community detection methods based on deep learning mainly include convolutional network, Graph Attention Network (GAT), AutoEncoder (AE), Deep Sparse Filtering (DSF) (Sperl, 2019), etc. For example, Chen et al. (2017) extended line graphs based on non-backtracking operators and proposed line Graph Neural Network model for community detection. Li et al. (2021) constructed an autoencoder to obtain a feature matrix that could represent network features, and used K-means algorithm to cluster the feature matrix to obtain community structure. Compared with the typical community detection algorithm, this algorithm has better effect and high time efficiency.

From the above analysis, it can be seen that although the method based on ranking has low time complexity and is suitable for dynamic networks, it needs to specify the number of communities according to prior knowledge, and the result is unstable. The probabilistic statistical model method is more stable and suitable for large-scale networks, but it does not solve the problem of overlapping communities. Meta-paths-based methods are simple and easy to understand. Multiple meta-paths can capture rich information in heterogeneous networks, but the obtained similarity is usually a deviation measure (Li et al., 2018). Moreover, how to select the optimal meta-path among multiple meta-paths to obtain the optimal partitioning effect is a difficult problem. Seed nodes-based method is a local calculation method, this method is easy to understand, suitable for large-scale network and dynamic network (Yakoubi & Kanawati, 2014), but there is still no consensus on how to efficiently select effective seed nodes, and when

merging non-seed nodes communities, there will be problems such as excessive merging of large communities and too many small communities. The extended modularity algorithm is evolved from the algorithm in the homogeneous network. It has high stability and is suitable for large-scale networks, but its network applicability is poor, and it still cannot avoid the limitation of modularity maximization -- resolution limitation, and it cannot detect small communities in large-scale networks (Fortunato & lemy, 2007; Lancichinetti & Fortunato, 2011; Liu et al., 2014). Although the homogeneous methods of heterogeneous networks methods are easy to understand, the process of reducing the dimensionality of heterogeneous networks to homogeneous networks is technically complex and frequently cause information distortion. Deep learning methods can encode the feature representation of high-dimensional data (Tian et al, 2014; Zhang, 2018), but the existing methods are more suitable for homogenous community structure, and the robustness of the model is limited (Jin et al., 2021).

Therefore, it can be seen that there is still a lot of space for further research on community detection methods in multi-node and multi-relation heterogeneous networks. This study will propose a community detection method that simultaneously utilizes network topology and text semantic information, the proposed method discovers all types of nodes and can identify overlapping communities.

Construction of academic heterogeneous network

In order to reveal the structure of science more accurately, combining the research of X.W. LIU on the characteristics of scientific communities and the existing network analysis content, the bibliometrics method was used to summarize the following categories (Table 2.1).

Table 2.1 Comparison of bibliometrics methods

Comparison item	Citation analysis		Co-authorship analysis	Keyword analysis
Unit of analysis	paper	author	author	keyword
Direct relation	paper-paper	author - author	author - author	keyword - keyword
Relation media type	paper recessive	paper recessive	paper dominant	keyword recessive
Space-time type	time	time	space	space

In citation analysis, paper citation analysis shows the relevance of paper content and describes the relationship between the development of disciplines on the timeline. Author citation analysis shows the transfer and transmission of tacit knowledge in the timeline, and can reveal the implicit correlation between authors. The analysis of co-authorship shows the sharing of knowledge among authors, which can clearly show the connection between authors. Keyword analysis is the coupling analysis of the keywords of the author's achievements to reveal the implied relationship between authors and the rules of knowledge exchange. Therefore, the combination of co-authorship and other relationships can explain the problems that cannot be obtained by single implicit and explicit relationships.

Nowadays, in the field of library and information, community detection research is mainly conducted on paper citation network and author cooperation network, particularly on the

analysis of homogeneous networks (Mena-Chalco et al., 2014; Bai et al., 2016; Hu & Ma, 2021). For the construction research of academic heterogeneous networks, K.W. Boyack (2010) studied co-citation network, paper coupling network and paper citation network, aiming to select the network that can best represent the trend of biomedical research. R. Rousseau et al. (2012) constructed a citations–citing authors–citing institutes–citing countries heterogeneous network to measure the degree of dissemination of scientific ideas. Liu et al. (2013) proposed a hierarchical framework for collaborative research, within the framework of a hierarchical article–author–institute–country heterogeneous network, examined the issue of collaboration and the resulting dissemination of shared knowledge. R. Dragomir (2016) constructed the network of paper citation, author citation and author cooperation based on ACL selection, and tried to find the most core paper and author through the analysis of network characteristic data, PageRank and other indicators. M. L. Liu (2018) constructed author citation relationship based on paper citation relationship to carry out effective academic recommendation. At present, the existing network construction is mostly a single network construction of author cooperation, paper citation, and institution cooperation. For the construction of heterogeneous academic network, there are still problems that the relationship construction is not comprehensive and deep enough, and the research of community detection based on heterogeneous academic network is still in the exploration. By contrast, this study constructs an academic heterogeneous network including author-paper writing, author cooperation, author citation and paper citation relationship, it can better comprehensively capture complex research communication and interaction, provide useful information for scientific evaluation and scientific decision-making (Yan & Ying, 2012).

Methods

This paper proposes an overlapping community detection method MESME-SLPA (Meta-path Extraction, Seednodes and Modularity Extension - SLPA Community Detection Method) based on meta-path extraction, seed nodes and extended modularity algorithm, in which, the improved SLPA Algorithm is used to identify overlapping communities. The specific steps are as follows: (1) Construct an academic heterogeneous network; (2) Calculate the edge weights between nodes based on the meta-path; (3) Select seed nodes; (4) Determine the labels of seed nodes according to modularity; (5) Determine the labels of non-seed nodes; (6) Final community detection based on improved SLPA label propagation algorithm. The specific process is shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Flow chart of MESME-SLPA method

Construct an academic heterogeneous network

Select multiple nodes according to requirements and build an academic heterogeneous network that includes relationships between nodes, the nodes may be papers (P), authors (A), keywords (K) or journals (C). The relationships between nodes include author-paper writing relationship, paper citation relationship, etc. As shown in Figure 3.2, we build a heterogeneous network with two node types (A, B).

Figure 3.2 Example of a heterogeneous network

Calculate edge weights between nodes based on meta-path

Meta-paths are extracted for two types of nodes A and B: A-A, A-B-B-A, B-b, etc., as shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3 Example of meta-path extraction

In the academic network, for the two types of nodes, author and paper, the relationship between authors can be connected by the following two meta-paths: "author-paper-author" means the author co-authored a paper, that is, the cooperative relationship between authors; "Author-paper-paper-author" indicates the citation relationship between authors. According to the node types existing in the academic network, Table 3.1 shows the meta-paths that may exist in nodes such as papers, authors, keywords, journals, etc. The specific edge weights calculation method is shown as follows.

Table 3.1 Meta-path selection and meaning

Meta-path	Relationship Meaning
$P \rightarrow A$	author-paper working
$P_i \rightarrow P_j$	paper citation
$P \rightarrow C$	paper-journal publication
$K \rightarrow P$	keyword-paper containing
$A_i \leftarrow P \rightarrow A_j$	co-authorship
$A_i \leftarrow P_i \rightarrow P_j \rightarrow A_j$	author citation

For the "paper-author" ($P \rightarrow A$) meta-path, the contribution of the author to the paper is calculated as the edge weight. Considering the practical operability, this study adopts the measurement method based on author signature order. Previous studies have proved that among the measurement methods based on author signature order, Harmoniccounting (HC) is more universal to the evaluation of scientific research workers (Fan & Xiao, 2015). Therefore, the harmoniccounting method is selected to calculate the contribution degree of each author to the paper. In the j th paper with N authors, the contribution of the i th author is:

$$Weight(A_i P_j) = \frac{\frac{1}{i}}{1 + \frac{1}{2} + \dots + \frac{1}{N}} \quad (3.1)$$

For the "paper to paper" ($P_i \rightarrow P_j$) meta-path, this paper uses LDA (Latent Dirichlet Allocation) topic model to model the title, abstract and keywords of the paper to obtain the topic probability vector, and then uses Jensen-Shannon (JS) distance function to calculate the similarity of the text topic probability vector as the edge weight value. Its calculation formula is shown in 3.2, p and q are the topic probability vectors of papers.

$$DJS(p,q)=\frac{1}{2}\left(\sum_{j=1}^k p_j \ln \frac{p_j}{q_j} + \sum_{j=1}^k q_j \ln \frac{q_j}{p_j}\right) \quad (3.2)$$

For the "paper-journal" (P→C) meta-path, because a paper is published in only one journal, the edge weight value of the paper-journal node is 1.

For the "keyword-paper" (K→P) meta-path, a paper contains multiple keywords, and the edge weight between each keyword and the paper is the reciprocal of the total number of keywords in the paper.

For the "author-paperary-author" (Ai←P→Aj) meta-path, that is, the author cooperation similarity is calculated according to the author-paper edge weight value, as shown in formula 3.3.

$$Simco(A_iA_j)=Sim(A_iP)*Sim(PA_j) \quad (3.3)$$

For the "author-paper-paper-author" meta-path (Ai←Pi→Pj→Aj), that is, the author citation similarity, the calculation method is shown in fomula 3.4, and the calculation is carried out according to the edge weight values of author-paper and paper-paper.

$$Simcit(A_iA_j)=Sim(P_iA_i)*Sim(P_iP_j)*Sim(P_jA_j) \quad (3.4)$$

For nodes with multiple meta-paths, multiple meta-paths are weighted and fused according to the occurrence probability of meta-paths. For the author-author node, there are two meta-paths: author cooperation and citation, the calculation formula is shown in 3.5. Where, α is the similarity fusion parameter, the existence probability is used to determine the weight, and the existence probability of the meta-path Ai←P→Aj and Ai←Pi→Pj→Aj is calculated respectively.

$$Weight(A_iA_j) = Sim(A_iA_j) = \alpha Simco(A_iA_j) + (1 - \alpha) Simcit(A_iA_j) \quad (3.5)$$

Community detection method

Selecting a seed node

The selection of seed nodes is the key link of heterogeneous networks community detection, which has a direct impact on the effect of community detection. Here, the seed nodes are selected according to the node strength, and the node strength is determined by the node degree and its second-order neighbors together. The computation formula is as follows, where Di, Dj represent the node degrees of nodes i and j respectively, Ni represents the neighbor nodes of node i, and Si represents the node strength of node i.

$$S_i = D_i + \sum_{j \in N_i} D_j \quad (3.6)$$

After calculating the intensity of all nodes, a class of them is selected as the central node type, and ranked top N in node intensity of this type are selected as the seed nodes. Where, N represents the percentage of the number of seed nodes in the total number of nodes, and the optimal value is determined by experiment.

A graphical example of the seed nodes selection is shown in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4 Example of seed nodes selection

Determine the labels of seed nodes

Community detection of seed nodes can obtain the number of communities in the entire network, and can simplify the calculation and reduce the complexity. Because the selected seed nodes are single-type nodes, the ready-made Leiden (Traag et al., 2019) algorithm is used to determine the label of the seed nodes to divide the seed community. This algorithm uses the node local movement algorithm to subdivide the community, which has advantages in terms of time consumption and community quality. In this study by calling in python Leidenalg packages to implement this algorithm, Traag to upload the source code of the algorithm in the Github (<https://github.com/vtraag/leidenalg>). Notes and questions can refer to the Leidenalg community (<https://github.com/vtraag/leidenalg/issues>).

Determine the labels of non-seed nodes

Based on the seed community obtained by dividing the seed nodes in the previous step, all the non-seed nodes are traversed, and the membership degree P of the non-seed nodes for each seed community is calculated, and it is added to the community with the largest P -value. The membership degree P -value is calculated as follows: if the neighbor nodes of the non-seed node exist in the seed community, the sum of the edge weights of the non-seed nodes and all the neighbor nodes in the seed community is calculated separately, and it is added to the seed community with the maximum sum of edge weights. If none of the neighbors of the non-seeded node is in the seed community, the non-seeded nodes will be added to the community of the node with the largest edge weight value. Determine the label of the non-seed node j according to the following formula:

$$L_j = \begin{cases} L_i, & i = \operatorname{argmax}_{i \in C_i} W_{ij}, \quad i \in N_j \\ L_j, & j = \operatorname{argmax} W_{ij}, \quad i \notin N_j \end{cases} \quad (3.7)$$

Where, i is the seed node, j is the non-seed node, L_i and L_j are the labels of node i and j respectively, W_{ij} represents the edge weight of node i and j , C_i represents the community to which seed node i belongs to, and N_j represents the neighbor node of non-seed node j .

Final community detection based on improved label propagation algorithm

Figure 3.5 Improved SLPA algorithm

The Speaker-Listener Label Propagation Algorithm (SLPA) is a community detection algorithm (Xie et al., 2011), which is an extension of Label Propagation Algorithm (LPA), as shown in Figure 3.5. SLPA introduces two concepts: information receiver (listener) and information provider (speaker). A node is randomly selected as a listener, and all its neighboring nodes are speakers. The specific steps of the improved SLPA algorithm are as follows:

- (1) Based on the above initial community detection, each node has an initial community label, and randomly selects nodes as listeners.
- (2) Calculate the occurrence times of each label in all the speakers of the listener. For each label, multiply its occurrence times by the edge weight between the two nodes, and select the label with the largest value and add it to the storage of the listener node. The storage stores the label and its occurrence times.
- (3) Repeat the above steps. After t rounds of iteration, if the number of labels of this node is 1, no screening will be carried out; otherwise, the labels with probability less than r in this node will be deleted, and the remaining labels will be used as the final node labels to realize the detection of overlapping community, where r is the threshold label occurrence probability.

The improved SLPA algorithm in this paper considers the edge weight of listener and each speaker as well as the number of label occurrences, selects the corresponding speaker node according to the product value of the two, sends and stores labels, and sets the threshold r so that the finally identified community can contain multiple labels, which can identify overlapping communities.

Figure 3.6 Example of overlapping communities

As shown in Figure 3.6, after a series of steps above, all nodes are finally divided into two mixed communities. Among them, the middle 3 nodes of class B nodes are overlapping nodes and belong to both communities, so community detection is completed.

Comparison of methods

In order to verify the effectiveness and feasibility of this method, this study selected DBLP dataset for verification, and selected the existing heterogeneous network community detection methods Hete-LPA, Hete_MESC (Zhang, 2017) and HCD_all (Shi & Yu,2017) for comparison.

Introduction to data sets

DBLP (DataBase systems and Logic Programming) (Shi & Yu,2017) dataset is an open bibliographic information collection that provides computer science journals and proceedings, mainly involving the following four areas: database, data mining, information retrieval and artificial intelligence, including author-paper writing relationship (A-P), paper-conference publication relationship (C-P), paper-term inclusion relationship (P-T), as shown in Figure 3.7. The dataset contains 14,376 articles, 20 conferences, 14,475 authors, 8,920 terms, and a total of 170,794 linked edges.

Figure 3.7 DBLP data

Experimental design

In order to prove the effectiveness of this algorithm, this study selects the existing classical and highly comparable heterogeneous network community detection algorithms, namely HETE-LPA, Hete_MESC, and HCD_all methods for comparison. As the author node is selected as the central node for community detection in these algorithms, the author is also selected as the central node here to construct A-P-A, A-P-T-P-A and A-P-C-P-A meta-paths around the author. The calculation method of edge weight among each node is as described in Section 3.2 above. Among them, Hete-LPA method and HCD_all method both use LPA label propagation algorithm for community detection. Compared with LPA algorithm, the biggest feature of SLPA algorithm improved in this study is that it can record the historical label sequence of each node in the process of refreshing iteration, and can identify overlapping communities. Hete_MESC method realizes community detection based on seed nodes, but it only realizes the identification of the initial community. These three methods have something in common with the method proposed in this study, so the selection of these three algorithms can carry out a more targeted comparison.

Comparison of results

To assess accuracy, this study used DBLP_four_area data annotated by Gao et al. (2009). Since the real community detection results are known, Normalized Mutual Information NMI (Santos & Embrechts, 2009) and modularity Q (Newman & Girvan, 2004) indicators are selected in this study to evaluate the community detection results, and the results are as follows.

Table 3.2 Comparison of experimental results of different community classification methods

Method	NMI	Q
Hete-LPA	0.5799	0.4997
HCD_all	0.6797	0.5412
Hete_MESC	0.7363	0.5492
MESME-SLPA	0.8125	0.5734

The experimental results show that the MESME-SLPA method in this study is higher than others in NMI and Q value, and the community detection effect is better, which has certain advanced nature.

In summary, the proposed MESME-SLPA method is an academic heterogeneous network community detection method based on meta-path, seed nodes and extended modularity. The method has the following three characteristics: (1) it simultaneously utilizes network topology and text semantic information. (2) it can meet the requirements of network mixture, and can simultaneously detect the community of all types of nodes according to the relationship between nodes. (3) It can identify overlapping communities.

Empirical research

In order to fully and clearly reveal the scientific community, scientific research structure, and the development context of a certain discipline, this study selected the field of "gene editing technology", constructs a heterogeneous network as shown in Figure 4.1: two types of nodes—paper and author, four relationships—paper and author working, author cooperation, paper citation and author citation. This network strengthens the direct connection between authors and their research content, and can simultaneously reveal the longitudinal cooperation information of the author in the time axis and the horizontal citation association in the space. Subsequently, we carried out the community detection.

Figure 4.1 Paper-Author heterogeneous network

Gene editing field selection

This study selected the data in the field of "gene editing technology" as the analysis object. It was born in the early 1980s. Nowadays, with the continuous optimization and development of "gene editing technology", it has great application prospects in the fields of disease diagnosis and treatment, crop breeding, energy and material development, virus nucleic acid detection and so on.

The data in this field is selected as the research object, on the one hand, because of its accessibility and applicability. On the other hand, the core researchers in this field are distinct, mainly including scientist Zhang Feng, Nobel Prize winner Emmanuelle Charpentier and Jennifer A. Doudna, etc. Community detection of academic groups in this field is conducive to the verification of the results and has a certain guiding role in understanding the subsequent development of the discipline.

Data acquisition and preprocessing

Data acquisition

In this paper, Web of Science database (core collection) was selected and the following retrieval method was used: TS=(((Genome OR Gene OR Genetic OR DNA OR RNA) NEAR/2 Editing) OR "base editing" OR Meganuclease* OR "Homing Endonuclease*" OR "Zinc Finger Nuclease*" OR ZFN* OR (Transcription* Activator* Like Effector Nuclease*) OR ((Genome OR Gene OR Genetic OR DNA OR RNA) AND (TALEN* OR (TALE* AND "Transcription Activator*")))) OR "Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeat*" OR CRISPR*), Article OR Review OR Proceedings; The retrieval date was June 2020, and 25,829 plain text records were finally exported.

Data preprocessing

A total of 25,826 articles were obtained after preliminary cleaning of the obtained paper data, removing unsigned authors, retraction and duplicate records of papers. Considering to the

tractability of data and the visualization of the constructed network, we select highly cited papers and high-influence authors to carry out the research. Selecting highly cited papers as the main research objects can reflect the scientific research frontiers and subject hotspots in the field. Therefore, this study screened out highly cited papers by Price index, and calculated the minimum citation frequency of highly cited papers by using formula 4.1. n_{max} represents the highest citation frequency of all papers, m is the minimum citation frequency of selected highly cited papers, and finally 1300 highly cited papers were screened out according to this condition.

$$m = 0.749 * \sqrt{n_{max}} \quad (4.1)$$

In addition, in order to improve the pertinence of the analysis, only the corresponding authors were studied. That is, for a paper, as long as its author has served as the corresponding author in the local dataset, it will be selected. In general, the corresponding author is usually the leader of research team, and the proposer of key research ideas. The social network analysis of the corresponding authors can effectively reveal the cooperation, citation and community situation of the research team.

Then, we used Derwent Data Analyzer software (DDA v7, Search Technology Inc., Norcross, GA, USA) and manual verification method to clean the author fields based on AU (author abbreviation), AF (author's full name), ADR (author's address), OI (ORCID), EM (corresponding author's email) fields in the downloaded dataset. The references were cleaned according to the CR (reference), DI (DOI number), AU (author abbreviation), JI (publication name abbreviation) and PY (publication year) fields in the downloaded dataset. A total of 1300 highly cited references and 891 corresponding authors were obtained.

Author - paper heterogeneous network community detection

For the paper-author heterogeneous network, four meta-paths were constructed as shown in Table 4.1, P represents the paper node, and A represents the author node. Based on the following four meta-paths, we calculate its edge weights and construct author-paper writing, paper-paper citation, author-author cooperation and author-author citation network.

Table 4.1 Meta-path selection and meaning

Meta-path	Relationship meaning
P→A	author-paper working
P _i →P _j	paper citation
A _i ←P→A _j	co-authorship
A _i ←P _i →P _j →A _j	author citation

Author-paper heterogeneous network community detection evaluation metrics

There are many kinds of evaluation indexes for the effect of community detection, and different evaluation indexes are used for different experimental needs. Since this study does not know the true partitioning results and needs to evaluate the discovery effect of overlapping communities, the extended modularity (EQ) index (Xie et al., 2011) is adopted. The value range of EQ is [0,1], and the larger the value, the better the effect of community detection. The calculation formula is as follows.

$$EQ = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{ij} \frac{1}{Q_i Q_j} \left[A_{ij} - \frac{k_i k_j}{2m} \right] \delta(C_i, C_j) \quad (4.2)$$

Among them, i and j are any two nodes, Q_i and Q_j represent the number of nodes belonging to the community, k_i and k_j are the degrees of nodes i and j respectively, and m is the total number of edges in the network. When two nodes are directly connected, $A_{ij}=1$, otherwise $A_{ij}=0$. C_i and C_j are the communities to which nodes i and j belong to, respectively. If the two nodes belong to the same community, then $\delta=1$, otherwise $\delta=0$.

Experimental results

According to the above heterogeneous network community detection steps, community detection is performed on the author-paper heterogeneous network. Table 4.2 summarizes the parameters involved in this study.

Table 4.2 Empirical research parameters

Parameter	Meaning	Value range
Seednode_type	seed nodes type	author, paper
Seednode_num	seed nodes number	10%-100%
r	label occurrence probability	0.1-1.0
t	number of iterations	10-500

In the initial experiment, the number of iterations of all experiments was set 10, and four experiments were performed for the selection of the seed node type, the number of seed nodes, and the value of label occurrence probability. Among them, Experiment 1 and Experiment 2 are the experimental results of selecting the author type node as the seed nodes, and Experiment 3 and Experiment 4 are the experimental results of selecting the paper type node as the seed nodes. The experimental results are shown in Figures 4.2 and Figures 4.3.

Figure 4.2 Comparison of the results of Experiment 1 and Experiment 3

Figure 4.3 Comparison of the results of Experiment 2 and Experiment 4

According to the experimental results, we find when the paper node is selected as the seed node type, the number of seed nodes is 40%, the probability of label appearance is 0.3, and the number of iterations is 300, the highest modularity of community detection is 0.5467.

Discussion

The visualization of the community detection carried out is shown in Figure 5.1. We obtained that the author-paper heterogeneous network composed of a total of 2191 nodes and 33116 edges is finally divided into 382 communities and 24 overlapping nodes, of which the largest community contains 451 nodes, the minimum community is 2 nodes (a paper and its author). In order to better illustrate the effectiveness of this community detection method in author-paper heterogeneous network, removed the communities with less than 20 nodes, and analyzes the research direction of each community, main community nodes and overlapping nodes of the remaining six major communities.

Figure 5.1 Final community detection results

Community research direction

The word frequency of paper keywords in the community was counted to explore the research direction of the community, as shown in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1 Keyword statistics of Author-Paper Heterogeneous Network Community Research

Community label	Node number	Keyword
Com_1	351	CRISPR-Cas9、 Genome Engineering、 Zinc Finger Nuclease、 TALE Nuclease
Com_2	246	CRISPR、 Acquired resistance, Prokaryotes, Escherichia coli, Streptococcus thermophilus
Com_6	451	Zinc Finger Nuclease, TALE Nuclease, double-strand break, homologous recombination, CRISPR/Cas
Com_12	37	Somatic hypermutation, class transformation and recombination, active cytidine deaminase
Com_38	136	RNA editing, adenosine deaminase, double-stranded RNA,pre-mRNA
Com_98	35	Arabidopsis, mRNA, Plant-mitochondria, Gene editing

From the keywords in the research direction of each community, we can find that the existing research mainly focuses on the following three aspects: (1) Research of Zinc Finger Nuclease, activator like effector nuclease and CRISPR/Cas system. In recent years, ZFNs, TALENs and

CRISPR/Cas have been widely used in life science and medicine, such as gene therapy and transgenic breeding. (2) RNA editing technology, which has been on the rise in recent years, provides a new option for RNA therapy. RNA editing refers to the use of adenosine deaminase to perform single-base correction at the RNA level, it has advantages in the safety and scientific ethics of the treatment of a variety of diseases. (3) Mitochondrial gene editing technology. Modeling mitochondrial DNA mutations associated with disease would enable to treat mitochondrial derived diseases, so as to better understand the genetic changes related to cancer and aging.

Analysis of major community nodes

Representative nodes were selected for detailed analysis in the community 2 of the above 6 communities.

Figure 5.2 Visual display of Community 2

Table 5.2 Representative node analysis of Community 2

Node number	Corresponding literature/author	Corresponding author	Introduction
A2	Zhang, Feng	—	Tenured professor in the School of Science at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology
A3	Marraffini, Luciano A.	—	Study CRISPR/Cas immunity in bacteria.
A4	Doudna, Jennifer A.	—	Winner of the 2020 Nobel Prize in Chemistry.
A6	Charpentier,	—	Winner of the 2020 Nobel Prize in

	Emmanuelle		Chemistry.
A11	Horvath, Philippe		Winner of the 2018 Bauer Award for Scientific Achievement and Canada Gairdner Awards
A12	Barrangou, Rodolphe	—	Winner of Canada Gairdner Awards
A41	Koonin, Eugene V.	—	One of the ten most influential biomedical researchers.
P3	A Programmable Dual-RNA-Guided DNA Endonuclease in Adaptive Bacterial Immunity	A4; A5; A6	—
P6	CRISPR provides acquired resistance against viruses in prokaryotes	A11; A12; A13; A14	—
P44	The CRISPR/Cas bacterial immune system cleaves bacteriophage and plasmid	A12; A11	—

This community is mainly composed of Zhang, Feng(A2), Doudna, Jennifer A.(A4), Charpentier, Emmanuelle (A6). These researchers mainly studied the acquired immunity mechanism of CRISPR. Doudna, Jennifer A. and Charpentier and Emmanuelle won the 2020 Nobel Prize in Chemistry for developing the CRISPR/Cas9 genome-editing method. Meanwhile, the paper P3 co-authored by them analyzes the working principle of CRISPR system. It has a huge impact on the industry. Horvath, Philippe (A11) and Barrangou, Rodolphe (A12) established a cooperative relationship through their paper P6 and P44. At the same time, they won the Canada Gairdner Awards together, which is called the little Nobel Award, because of their work in creating and describing CRISPR/Cas bacteriological immune defense system.

It is worth mentioning that Zhang, Feng, Doudna, Jennifer A. as the two most influential researchers in the field of gene editing technology, they are the most closely connected in the network. Although they have not co-authored papers, they have cited each other 267 times. Similarly, the authors of Doudna, Jennifer A. and Koonin, Eugene v. as well as Doudna, Jennifer A. and Marrafini, Luciano A., who are the second closest, have not cooperated in papers, and have generated 149 and 122 citations respectively. This shows their recognition of the achievements of both sides. It also indicates that the construction of the heterogeneous network has effectively excavated hidden communities and revealed potential authors who may cooperate in the future.

Overlapping node analysis

During community detection, this method selects labels with occurrence probability less than 0.3 to delete, and a total of 24 overlapping nodes were identified. It's statistically found that most of the community labels of nodes overlap with community 1 and community 6, community

2 and community 38. The specific labels are shown in Appendix A. The following mainly analyzes the overlapping nodes of community 2 and community 38, as shown in the Table 5.4.

Table 5.4 Overlapping nodes of Community 2 and Community 38

Node	corresponding to the author/paper	introduction
A266	Li, Jin Billy	Associate Professor of Genetics at Stanford, whose research focuses on understanding the regulation and function of RNA editing.
A463	Ramaswami, Gokul	Postdoctoral fellow in Genetics at Stanford with a focus on integrative genomics of autism spectrum disorders.

The research of authors Li and Jin Billy (A266) focuses on understanding the regulation and function of RNA editing. Their team uses an RNA fragment called "guide RNA to ADAR" to accurately edit RNA. The development of CRISPR/Cas technology has enabled the RNA editing system developed by combining ADAR enzymes and Cas enzymes can help ADAR enzymes to more accurately bind to specific RNA sequences. Li and Jin Billy team carried out research on this, so Li and Jin Billy are divided into community 2. Ramaswami, Gokul and Li, Jin Billy mainly carries out related research on the treatment of autism. The development of CRISPR/Cas technology makes it possible to knock out related autism risk genes, which provides a new idea for the treatment of autism. Therefore, they belong to community 2 and community 38 at the same time. The rise of new fields, theories and methods makes the research directions of researchers constantly expand and become more diverse, and the cooperation and citation among authors also promote the development and progress of CRISPR technology.

Conclusion

Research on heterogeneous networks is one of the most active research areas in recent years, and community structure is a common feature of heterogeneous networks, which are often composed of multiple communities. Community detection of heterogeneous networks can effectively reveal the structural characteristics, content attributes, and group distribution of the network. In this study, we select a multi-node and multi-relation academic heterogeneous network as the research object, integrate multiple relationships from multiple perspectives, use the network structure and rich link semantics among multiple types of nodes in the network to perform overlapping community detection. On the one hand, it can clearly reveal the academic community and the internal mechanism of its construction. On the other hand, the identification of overlapping communities can understand the changing trajectory of research direction of researchers to a certain extent, and can more accurately discover the cutting-edge research hotspots in the field, make contributions to broadening the breadth and depth of field research.

The main research work and contributions of this paper are as follows:

- (1) Clarify the concept of multi-node multi-relation heterogeneous networks and existed community detection methods. Existed community detection methods mostly suffer from unstable results, poor applicability to large-scale networks, information distortion, and unresolved overlapping community detection issues. This study analyzed the construction of academic heterogeneous networks and found that most existed networks only construct author

collaboration or literature citation relationships and perform single-node type network community detection. This study aims to explore new perspectives and construct a multi-type node multi-type relationship academic heterogeneous network for overlapping community detection.

(2) Propose the MEMES-SLPA community detection method suitable for large-scale multi-node multi-relation academic heterogeneous networks. This study proposes an overlapping community detection algorithm, namely MEMES-SLPA (MetaPath Extraction, Seednodes and Modularity Extension - SLPA Community Detection Algorithm). In summary, this method has the following four characteristics: It can simultaneously use network topology structure and text semantics information; It meets the requirements of network heterogeneity, where the heterogeneous network contains different types of nodes and different relationships, and the proposed method can perform community detection on all types of nodes based on the relationships between them; It can identify overlapping communities; It is suitable for large-scale networks.

(3) Construct an author-paper academic heterogeneous network. Unlike previous studies, this study selects two types of nodes: author and paper, constructs an academic heterogeneous network that includes author-paper authorship, paper citation, author collaboration, and author citation relationships. The network is divided into overlapping communities. On the basis of subdividing the results of community detection and mining out hidden communities, the scientific community and its inherent dynamic mechanism are revealed, and reveal the evolution of scholars' research directions through overlapping communities.

It is worth mentioning that, combined with the experimental results, we can find that this method still has the inherent defects of excessive consolidation of large communities and excessive number of small communities of seed nodes-based method. A total of 382 communities are detected, of which the largest community contains 451 nodes, the smallest community only has 2 nodes, and 303 communities only have 2 nodes. This is partly due to the selection of original data, in which 280 author-literature node pairs are isolated. At the same time, this study has a general effect on the identification of overlapping communities, and the number of overlapping communities identified is small. There are a total of 2191 nodes in this study, but under the condition that the probability of label occurrence is 0.3, only 24 overlapping nodes are identified, and the effect of identifying overlapping nodes is mediocre. Therefore, it is necessary to consider how to combine the effect of identifying the number of overlapping communities with the effect of community detection, so as to achieve a win-win situation, so as to explore the trend of research direction change of important authors.

In future works, we expect to solve the above problems by improving the edge weights calculation, add parameters restrictions, and carry out the research on dynamic network evolution of academic heterogeneous networks. According to the time slice, the community detection of heterogeneous networks in each time period is carried out to dynamically demonstrate the impact of the addition and deletion of author and paper nodes on the scientific structure over time.

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Appendix: Identification results of overlapping communities

Node	Community label 1	Community label 2	Node	Community label 1	Community label 2
A266	Com_2	Com_38	P1107	Com_277	Com_6
A289	Com_25	Com_38	P113	Com_1	Com_6
A424	Com_25	Com_38	P1268	Com_2	Com_38
A463	Com_2	Com_38	P277	Com_44	Com_38
A469	Com_233	Com_38	P382	Com_1	Com_6
A617	Com_321	Com_6	P522	Com_233	Com_38
A657	Com_25	Com_38	P549	Com_25	Com_38
A687	Com_361	Com_38	P632	Com_2	Com_38
A741	Com_6	Com_1	P633	Com_25	Com_38
A771	Com_2	Com_1	P678	Com_1	Com_6
P1071	Com_18	Com_38	P705	Com_2	Com_38
P1081	Com_1	Com_6	P798	Com_321	Com_6